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Severe anemia (hemoglobin 4 g/dL) in man without chronic disease

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ABSTRACT

We present a case of a male patient 46-year-old presented to the emergency department with a complaint of vomiting, cough, shivering and abdominal pain and a heart rate of approximately 97 beats per minute, and orthostatic blood pressure of 130/70 mm Hg upon standing. We report the lowest hemoglobin 4.0 g/dL was discovered by our laboratory.

Emergency department management of anemic and severe fatigue patients is common (1, 2). We report the lowest hemoglobin of which we are aware, at 4 g/dL, in a patient without chronic disease.

Case Report

Anemia is a serious global health problem that affects individuals of all ages but particularly women rather than men. Iron deficiency anemia is one of the most common causes of anemia (3). In this case report, a 46-year-old previously healthy man presented to the emergency department with a complaint of generalized fatigue and palpitations that had progressively increased over the last 10 days. The patient's heart rate was 97 to 100 beats/minute, and his blood pressure was 130/70mm Hg. He was found to have marked conjunctival pallor. He had generalized abdominal tenderness.

The patient had severe anemia with no history of sickle cell or other hematopoietic disorders. He denied bloody stools. He denied a history of hepatitis, intravenous drug use, prosthetic valves, or hemoptysis.

Initial laboratory evaluations were achieved by using standard laboratory protocols and a fully automated analyzer. A call by the emergency physician requesting the release of the results after two rejected attempts showed on the third specimen severe anemia with hemoglobin of 4.0 g/dL. (Tables 1 and 2) and (figure 1)

He was referred to the nearest hospital with facilities of blood bank service and transfused with appropriate units of blood over 2 days, reaching a hemoglobin level of 7.1 g/dL, and provided with intravenous and oral iron and *Jos-Pan Cough Syrup* 100 ml, *Klavox 625 Mg* tab, and *dumpy 10 mg* tablet.

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Table 1.

Hematological tests	Value	Reference range
Hemoglobin (g/dL)	4.0	12-17.4
Hematocrit (%)	13.78	36-52
Mean corpuscular volume (fL)	46	76-96
Mean corpuscular hemoglobin (pg)	11.9	27-34.5
Mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration (g/dL)	13.3	27-32
Mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration	29	30-35
Red cells distribution width	22.3	1.6-14.6%
Platelets	388	150-400
White blood cells	6.23	4- 11
Granulocytes %	55.5 %	50%-75%
Lymphocytes %	38.2 %	25 % - 40 %
Monocytes %	6.2 %	3.0% - 7.0 %

Table 2.

Chemical tests	Value	Reference range
Cholesterol	126	0 - 200
Creatinine	0.69	0-1.4
Glucose	115	75- 200
Aspartate Amino Transferase (AST), S.GOT	20	0-40
Alanine Amino Trasferase (ALT), S.GPT	8	0-42
Triglycerides	75	0-200
Uric acid	3.4	3.4- 7
Urea	30	10 - 50
Iron	1	37- 145

Figure 1.

A peripheral smear from the patient, small microcytic red blood cells are seen, many of which are hypochromic and have a large zone of pallor with a thin pink peripheral rim. A few characteristic poikilocytes (small elongated red cells also known as pencil cells) are also seen.

Discussion:

This patient presented with all the classic signs and symptoms of iron deficiency: anemia, fatigue, pallor, koilonychia, and labs revealing marked iron deficiency, microcytosis, elevated RDW, and low hemoglobin. To the best of our knowledge, this is the lowest recorded hemoglobin in an awake and alert man patient breathing ambient air. Our patient had the lowest men hemoglobin of which we are aware of in emergency and laboratory departments. Our patient lives in well nutritional community with advanced and fully supported health services with no chronic diseases, unlike another case that reported severe anemia (hemoglobin 3.7 g/dl) in infant patients due to malnutrition and severe COVID (4),

severe anemia at a level <4 g/dL is uncommonly seen in the health centers setting in the emergency and laboratory setting (5), but it has been reported in other case reports (6- 7), both of these cases were for women patients with choric diseases or surgery and malignancy. Another case has been reported of an ambulatory patient with a hemoglobin value less than 4.0 g/dl (8), and this was due to chronic urinary bleeding. The most common source or cause that leads to such severe anemia is iron deficiency, (9). His case adds to other case reports of patient survival with a hemoglobin level of <2 g/dl (5, 6, 10).

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that no conflict of interests.

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